

Strengthening Capacity to Address Climate Change for Small and Medium-sized City Development: People's Republic of China

Joohye Lim, Hwasoo Yeo

Civil and Environmental Engineering, Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology

INTRODUCTION

This is a research report that was done under guidance of Asia Development Bank (ADB), for sustainable urban development in People's Republic of China. In PRC, rapid urbanization is expected to accompany rapid increase of greenhouse gas emissions and accordingly serious environmental problems. The central government of the PRC was seeking for ways of low carbon development (LCD) to manage such problems, and had some notable efforts in reducing GHG emissions in large cities such as Beijing and Shanghai. However, small and medium-sized cities are far behind in terms of sustainable urban growth, while such cities are expected to get better and to expand very rapidly. Thus, the study was done to pursue LCD strategies to be suggested to PRC government, and the work was divided into four teams, such as urban management, land use and transport planning, energy, and waste and resource management. In this paper, KAIST team took land use and transportation planning. Along with national (Chinese) expert project coordinator, the study team attempts to increase SMC's energy efficiency while decreasing carbon emission per unit GDP. The aim of this study is to assist government in addressing climate change and urban LCD by strengthening the capacity of SMCs

THEORY AND METHOD

Figure 1 Concept of LCD

As shown in Figure 1, the first step was to re-define LCD. Especially in terms of land use and transport planning, we did in-depth research about the national trends, major barriers for LCD, review about policy review of LCD and GHG emissions in PRC. Then, according to newly defined LCD, we chose selection criteria of good practices to benchmark, which included financial support, residential participation. Then according to framework of selection criteria, among 100 practices, we could defined best-fitting practices for LCD in PRC.